

DESCRIPTION AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE LEXICO-SEMANTIC FIELD IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: In this article, the concept of the field is one of the effective tools for researching the lexical layer of the language, and this field is one of the most productive fields. It was studied that it is a complex of connected elements. Therefore, as a linguistic phenomenon, the field reflects the relationship between different levels of language. In addition, the linguistic significance of the relationship between field tools was also analyzed.

Key words: classification, Uzbek language, lexic, semantic, field, theory, system.

From the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, many scientific and theoretical works and opinions related to field interpretation began to appear in Uzbek linguistics. In this place, R. Rasulov, E. Begmatov, O. Bozorov, T. Mirzakulov, A. Nurmonov, Sh. Iskandarova, H. Ne'matov, I. Kochkartoev, R. Safarova, A. Sobirov, B. Qilichev, Sh. Rakhmatullaev, A. Hojiev, H. Hojieva, M. Abdiev, J.B. Boronov, Sh. Safarov, O'. Kadirov, O'. Q. Yusupov, S. Rahimov, G. Khoshimov, J. A. Yakubov, M. Abduvaliev, Sh. Shokirov, etc. scientific observations and scientific conclusions obtained on this basis are of great importance in the study of the lexicon, morphology and syntax of Uzbek and other world languages based on field theory. By lexical-semantic field, we mean a complex lexical microsystem. This microsystem has a unique field structure and combines words based on the semantic principle. One of the characteristic features of the lexical-semantic field is that it includes the concept of the central field and its peripheral part away from the center, and the field is arranged hierarchically, that is, in a stepped order.

Semantic field is the largest lexical-semantic paradigm of different word groups that have a common lexical meaning and are compatible with each other in reflecting objective reality. The functional-semantic field is a system of a general character organized in a lexical-syntactical way, as well as tools belonging to different layers of the language (morphological, syntactic, word-forming tools, lexical).

Macrocomponents determine the main feature of word semantics and can be distinguished by semantic opposition of lexical units. In the lexical sense of the word, experts distinguish two types of macrocomponents: denotative and connotative components. The denotative component is the main component of the lexical meaning, it embodies a communicatively important object-concept, it means the sign and characteristics of the named thing (subject). The connotative macrocomponent represents the speaker's emotional evaluation attitude towards the denotation, as well as functional-stylistic features, that is, it shows the functional style of the word. Denotative and connotative macrocomponents separate microcomponents from their composition.

Below is an opinion about the introduction of field theory into Uzbek linguistics, certain advantages of looking at the content system of the language as a field, the characteristics of the field, its difference from other related phenomena, some microfields that have a certain place in the content system of the Uzbek language is conducted.

The field theory allows the people who speak that language to fully understand the main fund of words (lexical units) used in the process of communication in a certain area of life, to find the words needed from this system in the process of communication. provides a choice and ensures that these words are related to each other in terms of meaning.

The functional-semantic field is a system of a general character, organized in a lexical and lexical-syntactic sense, with tools belonging to different layers of the language (morphological, syntactic, word-forming tools). The functional-semantic

field is bilateral, i.e., it is a whole that is connected with each other in a two-sided character and has not only a meaning plane, but also an expression plane.

Lexeme - the relationship between a word and a concept is called a significant relationship, and the meaning that emerges as a result of this relationship is called a conceptual meaning. The concept is a logical category, and it is important in our rational understanding of the world.

In her work, Sh. Iskandarov points out several theoretical issues that are defined by linguists in the same way, despite the different approaches to the meaningful field and the diversity among researchers:

- 1) the structure of the language dictionary does not consist of a random collection of units, it is divided into a number of meaningful areas that are united based on the semantic commonality of words;
- 2) each meaningful field divides the entity it reflects into its components in a special way unique to this language;
- 3) the semantic content of a word is not considered something that comes from itself, it arises through conflicts with other words (units) in the field.

In her book, Sh. Iskandarova deeply analyzed a number of semantic fields: temporality, locality, microfield, condition, non-obstacle microfields, and illustrated them with various examples.

In recent years, studies based on the onomasiological principle and based on the approach to the content of the language as a field have become very popular in Uzbek linguistics. For example, A. Sobirov approached the lexical level as a meaningful field in his scientific research work on the topic "Research of the lexical level of the Uzbek language as a system", N. Nishonova analyzed the semantic analysis of certain microfields in the lexical level, H. Hojjeva and F. Safarov paid attention to the structural analysis of units specific to different levels in the content structure.

B.Yoldoshev stated that "combining the lexical units of the language into certain meaningful series (cells) and writing artistic-historical or linguistic works based on

them is directly related to the name of the Eastern world, in particular, Turkish-speaking writers and specialists. For example, in "Boburnoma" together with the image of India, zoonyms, ornithonyms, phytonyms, etc. of that region are classified by topic groups using the principle of semantic field. Also, Muhammad Yaqub Changi, who served in the court of Baburi prince Aurangzeb, used the principle of creating a thematic and cellular dictionary when compiling his dictionary called "Kelurnoma".

The issue of grouping simple and complex lexemes based on their expressed meanings, their mutual and semiotic relationship with other words is not being raised today. This issue has attracted the attention of scientists for a long time.

Description and classification of field theories in Uzbek linguistics. From the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, many scientific-theoretical works and views related to field interpretation began to appear.

The well-known typologist, professor O'.Q. Yusupov, in his scientific treatise "Теоретические основы сопоставительное лингвистики" developed a research methodology in order to create the theoretical foundations of cross-linguistics. It is said that translational, logical, field, topological, denotative approaches can be used in the comparison of languages. In this pamphlet, the author expresses his personal opinion about the principles of determining the scale of the field, the analysis methods of its components, while providing important analytical information about the founders of field theory, their scientific concepts in this regard.

Determining the five different aspects between the concepts seen in the previous chapter, O'.Q. Yusupov rightly emphasizes that these concepts do not negate each other, on the contrary, they complement each other.

Comparing the corresponding semantic fields requires determining the following, says O'.Q. Yusupov:

- similarities and differences in the inventory of words;
- lexical-semantic groups;

- synonymous lines;
- antonym pairs and lacunae;

Similar and different features between equivalent words included in the field should also be determined, the brochure says. It is also noted that they are determined by the following parameters:

- form (expression plan),
- semantic structure,
- meaningful volume of meanings,
- valency,
- limb,
- frequency,
- synonymous, antonym and hyponym relations,
- lexical-grammatical feature,
- primary (secondary) meaning,

Comparing the content of the corresponding words requires determining the denotative and connotative meanings of the terms, the issue of the core and periphery of the terms. Meanings that do not exist in the semantics of the languages being compared indicate the uniqueness of the semantics of the national language.

O. Q. Yusupov believes that the word "bread" in Uzbek is not the same as its equivalent in Russian, хлеб. He says that the semantic structure of the words "race" in English and "irq" in Uzbek is not the same. He says that "irq" (paca) in Uzbek language has several meanings besides "race" (paca) in English. These are the words "род", "племя", "народ" "происхождение", "порода", "сорт", "аромат", "расовый", "национальный".

Regarding the valence of words, the author cites the words strong and strong as an example: strong wind - heavy rain, strong wind - heavy rain. It is clear that the word strong, unlike the word strong, cannot come with the word rain.

The number of words included in the field is often not the same. Such inconsistency is evidence of the fact that the segmentation and categorization of existence, traditions, and people's way of life are different.

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